

Review and Comparison of Associative Classification Data Mining Approaches

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Abstract : Data mining is one of the main phases in the Knowledge Discovery Database (KDD) which is responsible of finding hidden and useful knowledge from databases. There are many different tasks for data mining including regression, pattern recognition, clustering, classification, and association rule. In recent years a promising data mining approach called associative classification (AC) has been proposed, AC integrates classification and association rule discovery to build classification models (classifiers). This paper surveys and critically compares several AC algorithms with reference of the different procedures are used in each algorithm, such as rule learning, rule sorting, rule pruning, classifier building, and class allocation for test cases.

Keywords : associative classification, classification, data mining, learning, rule ranking, rule pruning, prediction

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